

ISic1198

I.Sicily inscription 1198

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tyndaris

Place of origin (modern)

Tindari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Copenhagen, Denmark, Ny Carlsberg Glyptotek, inventory IN 0516

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140682

1. Πρῶτος καὶ Μενίππη Ἀρτέμιδι Εὐπραξίαι.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492802

EDCS 39101562

PHI 140682

Bibliography

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